

IAF SYMPOSIUM ON INTEGRATED APPLICATIONS (B5)
Integrated Commercial Satellite Applications for Sustainability and Climate (3)

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ADVANCING CARBON FARMING INITIATIVES WHILE SAFEGUARDING BIODIVERSITY,
WATER RESOURCES, AND SOIL HEALTH THROUGH EARTH OBSERVATION AND EMERGING
TECHNOLOGIES: THE INNO4CFIS PROJECT

Abstract

The environmental and climatic challenges of the 21st century demand innovative, science-driven solutions. Carbon farming has gained momentum as a viable strategy to enhance the sustainability of agricultural and forestry practices. By integrating agroforestry techniques that optimize land use and promote tree-planting initiatives, this approach bolsters carbon sequestration while reducing greenhouse gas emissions, thus supporting global climate action. Now entering its second year, the INNO4CFIS project—“Nature-Based Business Models and Emerging Innovations to Strengthen Carbon Farming Initiatives (CFIs) While Preserving Biodiversity, Water Security, and Soil Health”—coordinated by the E. Amaldi Foundation, has made significant strides in developing a Carbon Farm Technology Platform. This platform harnesses Earth Observation (EO) technologies, artificial intelligence (AI), and advanced carbon-tracking tools, validated through five European pilot ecosystems encompassing a minimum of 6,000 trees and biological species. Building upon AI-enhanced EO datasets, the project integrates hyperspectral, multispectral, and LiDAR imaging, achieving centimeter-scale precision in analyzing the interaction between carbon sequestration techniques and spectral reflectance (400-900nm) of soil and vegetation. This high-resolution data is further augmented with satellite imagery from open-access platforms, delivering a 10m resolution with a 5-day revisit cycle, alongside auxiliary data from meteorological stations, UAV-based monitoring, and mycelium-inspired carbon tracking innovations. These combined datasets fuel predictive models that simulate carbon capture dynamics based on evolving land cover, continuously validated against real-time field data. Over the past year, INNO4CFIS has advanced its methodologies by refining machine learning algorithms, enhancing the precision of carbon sequestration estimations, and expanding its peer-to-peer carbon credit exchange system, leveraging blockchain technology for secure and transparent transactions. By aligning with EU Green Deal objectives, the project plays a crucial role in combating deforestation, biodiversity decline, drought-related risks, and soil degradation. This paper explores the impact and scalability of the INNO4CFIS Carbon Farm Technology Platform integrated into the Interregional Market Uptake Hub (IMUH), highlighting how its integration of EO, AI, and blockchain fosters more effective, measurable, and sustainable carbon farming initiatives. The discussion aligns with the broader context of integrated commercial satellite applications, demonstrating how space-based data solutions can support sustainability goals, enhance climate resilience, and drive forward the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).